

WORKSHOP 4: Barriers & opportunities for broader change

Date: 13.11.2024

Duration: 4 hours

Number of participants: 6 people

Profile of participants: Young people 20-28 years old, residing in Germany (Thuringia) coming from EU and non-EU countries

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Workshop Report

The fourth workshop was held at the Culture Goes Europe shared office space, bringing together both longstanding and new members of the Learning Community. To ensure everyone was aligned, the session began with a comprehensive review of the project timeline, revisiting key workshops and episodes. This included an overview of the theory behind leverage points, interventions, and indicators, reflections on the game-testing sessions, and insights from the Youth4Biodiversity package intervention. Following this recap, participants engaged in a dynamic discussion to synthesize their understanding of these concepts and prepare for the workshop's main focus: exploring barriers and opportunities for broader change. The core activity involved analyzing three interventions—the Biodiversity-Food-Governance Game, the Hike, and the Outdoor Cinema—across several dimensions: the systems that could be influenced by each intervention; the potential for broader impact; opportunities (factors, actors, and processes) that could facilitate change; and barriers (factors, actors, and processes) that could obstruct it.

Photos of the Learning Community meeting on 13.11.24 taken by Maryna Bykova.

The Learning Community followed the steps proposed in the methodology guide, developing answers to each category and for each intervention.

Photo of the table developed by the Learning Community of Urban Youth case study.

The following table presents the compiled content:

	Other Systems	Broader Impact	Opportunities	Barriers
BFG Game	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumer habits transformation - Publishing industry - School System/Formal Education - Bring the game to big corporations and "higher" positions – to test it with other target groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing Knowledge of ecological matters - Multiplier effect potential - Learning tool for youth workers within non-formal education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To create campaigns, movements, and awareness – for change - Capacity-building and cooperation with other NGO's interested in this methodology - Utilizing networks of NGO's to aim at different groups - Diversifying the methodology for knowledge transmission - Place for discussions, reflections, changing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for capacity-building of teachers - Lack of knowledge from the young people – lack of motivation - Should be integrated into a larger system of change, where the reflections/empowerment are taken and used for further action - Lack of interest from the public

			thought patterns and attitudes	
Hike	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alternative medicine / changing health policies - Public health care system – less burden - School system – alternative contexts - Farmers and rural villagers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of migrant community – nature as a common ground - Regular daily activity - Creating stronger communities - Encourage people to walk more 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monetize nature exploration – more work opportunities - Physical exercise - Development of mental health and resilience - Development of hard skills – independence and empowerment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of natural environment - Trash, fire risk, leaving too many human traces – destroying nature - Need for trained guides /knowledge of routes - Risk of and for animals - People may not like being in strict contact with nature - Lack of accessibility/information
Outdoor Cinema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cinema industry - Parks/natural places – new opportunities - Breaking barriers in “cinema academy” policy and discourse - Educational system – new ways for diversifying audience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Closer connection with nature - Discussion with different groups – emotional bond through fun moments - Promoting small underground movies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bringing groups together: interested in art and interested in nature - Open access – easy access - Have fun - Learn about different topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of knowledge of access to quality movies - Weather/environment - Need for material and those working with the material

The following provides a description and summary of the content developed by the learning community, as well as insights from the ongoing discussions during its creation.

1. Biodiversity-Food-Governance Game

Other systems: The BFG Game was identified as a tool with significant potential to influence multiple systems and foster broader change in ecological awareness. Among the systems potentially impacted are consumer habits, the game publishing industry, formal and non-formal education, with opportunities for integration into school curricula and corporate or community environments to reach diverse audiences. Additionally, the game introduces new teaching methodologies that could enrich school programs, after-school initiatives, and NGO-led youth engagement activities. By promoting interactive and interdisciplinary learning, such as combining governance concepts with emotional bonding exercises, the game offers a dynamic platform for both formal and non-formal education systems.

Broader impact: The game’s broader impact includes its ability to enhance ecological knowledge and act as a multiplier effect for spreading awareness. It also encourages critical thinking about governance, consumption patterns, and their societal implications, fostering political awareness alongside ecological consciousness. Schools and communities adopting the game would generate a significant pool of informed citizens who understand the intersections of biodiversity, food systems, and governance, creating a demand for aligned policies. Scaling the game could normalise citizen engagement in policymaking by illustrating governance principles in an accessible format. This may lead to grassroots movements pushing for policies that reflect the priorities highlighted during gameplay. Research on the game’s outcomes (e.g., improved ecological literacy, behavior change) could provide data to justify policy changes.

Opportunities: Key opportunities highlighted include creating campaigns and movements to promote ecological consciousness, fostering cooperation with NGOs, and utilizing existing networks to expand its reach. By integrating the game into school curricula, it can inspire broader adoption of interactive, experiential learning methods in formal education systems. This could lead to national and regional mandates to incorporate environmental governance topics as core subjects.

Additionally, the game offers the potential to be scaled through partnerships with other non-governmental organisations, creating multipliers/game facilitators for its impact. Diversifying the methodology to suit different contexts, such as integrating it into interdisciplinary education approaches, and providing platforms for reflection and discussion were seen as crucial for shifting perspectives and attitudes.

Barriers: However, several barriers were noted. Scaling the game would require capacity building for educators and teachers, prompting policies to include teacher certification programs focused on innovative, non-traditional methodologies. Lack of knowledge (information about the activity) and lack of motivation among young people (assuming that not everyone is a member of “Fridays for Future”, as well as one needs to have patience to learn about the extensive rules of the game before playing it) to participate in such game could be another barrier.

Resistance in formal education systems, particularly in regions where external methodologies are not easily accessible, was also highlighted as a potential hurdle.

2. Hike

Other systems: The hike emerged as an intervention capable of influencing various systems and promoting broader environmental and community impacts. Systems influenced by the hike include healthcare, where regular hiking supports both physical and mental well-being, potentially reducing health system burdens. Additionally, it fosters community building, as shared hiking experiences strengthen interpersonal connections and cultivate a sense of belonging. The hike also has implications for tourism and environmental conservation, as scaling the activity could boost eco-tourism while promoting biodiversity preservation.

Broader impact: The hike’s broader impacts extend to encouraging active lifestyles, which can indirectly influence health and wellness industries. By immersing participants in natural settings, supported by a guided narration about the environment observed, it has a potential to cultivate environmental stewardship and a deeper appreciation for biodiversity. On a larger scale, successful implementation could inspire infrastructural changes, such as the development of more accessible hiking trails, encourage wider community participation, e.g. by bringing in migrant communities, urban youth, and promote sustainable outdoor practices.

Opportunities: Opportunities associated with the hike include establishing regular community-led hiking initiatives to sustain momentum and engagement. Partnering with local governments and organizations to map and promote trails can amplify accessibility and outreach. Furthermore, leveraging hiking events as educational opportunities provides a platform to inform participants about biodiversity, conservation practices, and sustainable behaviors.

Barriers: However, several barriers must be addressed for broader adoption. Accessibility remains a significant challenge, particularly for individuals with disabilities or those living in urban or industrialised regions. Safety concerns in remote or undeveloped hiking areas, as well as potential environmental degradation from overuse or mismanagement of trails, also pose significant hurdles. Mitigating these risks requires thoughtful planning and community engagement to ensure hiking remains both inclusive and sustainable.

3. Outdoor Cinema

Other systems: The outdoor cinema intervention demonstrated its potential to influence multiple systems and foster greater ecological awareness and community engagement. Systems influenced include culture and entertainment, as the outdoor cinema provides an innovative platform/place for community gathering and education through film. It also promotes environmental awareness, with films on ecological themes deepening participants' understanding and connection to biodiversity issues. Additionally, the intervention fosters community engagement by creating inclusive spaces for shared experiences and follow-up group reflection, seamlessly linking entertainment with learning.

Broader impact: The broader impact of the outdoor cinema can include an appreciation for nature while being surrounded by it in a movie screening location. Birds' singing, leaves moving by the wind, natural ground – all add-up to an experience of film watching. Additionally, by creating demand on embedding biodiversity themes into the cinematography, we could potentially influence the film industry to create more content addressing sustainability and conservation. The intervention also offers a replicable model for other communities, blending environmental education with leisure activities to reach a wider audience.

Opportunities: Key opportunities identified include hosting diverse films (different genre, scale – from amateur to Academy-winning - and country of production, different language used in the narration, etc.) to attract varied audiences, thereby appealing to both environmental enthusiasts and those with a general interest in cinema.

Partnering with local environmental groups could further strengthen the connection between cinema events and conservation efforts, potentially sparking action on a broader scale. Local activists and experts could be invited to join a discussion after the movie, attending Q&A, offering a safe space for audience to raise their voices and possibility to question the expertise-holders.

Additionally, creating a mobile cinema unit could expand the geographic reach, bringing this unique experience to underserved or rural populations.

Barriers: However, several barriers must be considered. Logistical challenges, such as sourcing equipment (laptop, projector, electricity station), navigating weather conditions, and ensuring safety (for the environment and participants), can complicate the organisation of outdoor cinema events. Furthermore, license for screening and the availability of quality films that align with biodiversity themes and are in local languages (or with subtitles) remains limited, presenting an additional obstacle to scaling this intervention.